

*19th Chaotic Modeling
and Simulation
International Conference*

CHAOS 2026

12 - 15 Jun, 2026

Book of Abstracts

**Venue: Hellenic Mediterranean University
Department of Management and Technology
Lakonia Campus
Agios Nikolaos, Crete, Greece**

2 *Book of Abstracts, CHAOS2026 International Conference*

Contents

	<i>Page</i>
<i>Preface</i>	3
<i>Plenary Talks</i>	5
<i>Special Sessions</i>	9
<i>Invited Talks</i>	
<i>Index</i>	

Preface

Dear Guests, Dear Colleagues,

We welcome you to the 19th Chaotic Modeling and Simulation International Conference -CHAOS 2026 in Agios Nikolaos.

As the previous years, a considerable number of high-quality research papers are accepted for oral or poster presentations.

Important speakers present onsite and virtually their work promoting scientific development and research.

We have submissions from 33 countries: Algérie, Austria, Belarus, Brasil, Bulgaria, Canada, Czech Republic, France, Greece, Hungary, India, Israel, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Malta, Mexico, New Zealand, Nigeria, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, South korea, Spain, Sweden, Turkey, United Kingdom, Ukraine, USA, Uzbekistan.

I'd like to thank the Committees of the Conference which worked hard for this success.

I'd also like to thank the Region of Crete, our Sponsor.

Dr Christos H. Skiadas
ex- vice Rector
Technical University of Crete
Chair of ISAST

***Adiabatic Theory of Strongly Chirped
Dissipative Solitons***

**Vladimir L. Kalashnikov¹, A. Rudenkov¹, E. Sorokin², I.
T. Sorokina¹**

¹*Department of Physics, NTNU, Trondheim, NO-7491, Norway*

²*Institut für Photonik, TU Wien, Gusshausstraße 27/387, Vienna, A-1040, Austria*

Abstract

We present the adiabatic theory for strongly chirped dissipative solitons in the cubic–quintic complex Ginzburg–Landau equation, with an emphasis on physically transparent energy (mass)-scalability criteria for the dissipative soliton (DS) laser oscillators and metaphoric modeling of Bose-Einstein condensates. The proposed adiabatic approximation and regularization techniques yield closed-form solutions for the peak power, energy, and stationary-phase spectra of DSs. That provides a compact dimensionless mapping of the soliton existence domains in both the normal- (NGD) and anomalous group-delay dispersion (AGD) regimes. A central outcome is that the DS resonance (DSR), which means a chirp-driven temporal stretching at bounded peak power, arises naturally in both regimes. The DSR is associated with the DS energy divergence in the master diagram of the DS parameter space. We show that DSR persists in NGD for a finite quintic self-phase modulation. In AGD, DSR occurs within the adiabatic existence window, beginning from a finite level of quintic self-phase modulation. The analytically derived spectral profiles (the truncated Rayleigh–Jeans-like in NGD and algebraically tailed

in AGD) enable a thermodynamic characterization of DS and provide quantitative indicators of resonance, breakup onset, and transitions to multi-soliton states.

Norges Forskningsråd supported this work (#303347 (UNLOCK), #326503 (MIR)). We acknowledge using the IDUN NTNU scientific cluster.

Keywords: Dissipative Soliton, Cubic-Quintic Complex Ginzburg-Landau Equation, Adiabatic Approximation, Dissipative-Soliton Resonance, Chirped-Pulse Oscillators, Thermodynamics of Non-Equilibrium Dissipative Systems

A Fractional-Order Dynamics of Societal Sustainability: A Study on Memory Effects and Predictability in the HANDY Model

Engin Kandıran¹, A.S. Hacınlıyan²

1 Department of Software Development, Faculty of Computer and Information Sciences, Yeditepe University, Istanbul, Turkey

2 Faculty of Computer and Information Sciences and Rectorate, Yeditepe University, Istanbul, Turkey

Abstract

This study proposes a fractional-order extension of the Human and Nature Dynamics (HANDY) model, originally developed by Motesharrei et al. [1], to incorporate power-law memory effects into the simulation of societal sustainability and resource use. While the original model employs four integer-order differential equations to represent the interaction between commoners, elites, nature, and wealth, the proposed fractional framework accounts for historical consumption habits and delayed ecological responses. To overcome the analytical bottlenecks posed by the system's inherent discontinuities—specifically in consumption thresholds and death rates—we utilize the numerical smoothing methodology established in previous studies by Hacınlıyan and Kandıran [2]. By

Adiabatic Theory of Strongly Chirped Dissipative Solitons

Normal and anomalous dispersion regimes in the cubic–quintic
CGLE

Vladimir L. Kalashnikov¹, A. Rudenkov¹, E. Sorokin^{2,3}, I. T. Sorokina^{1,3}

¹Department of Physics, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, 7491 Trondheim, Norway

²Institut für Photonik, TU Wien, Gußhausstraße 27/387, A-1040 Vienna, Austria

³ATLA lasers AS, Richard Birkelands vei 2B, 7034 Trondheim Norway

chirped DS

Why strongly chirped dissipative solitons?

- **Dissipative solitons** are localized states maintained by nonlinear gain/loss and dispersion/self-phase modulation balances.
- **Strong chirp** allows temporal stretching while peak power remains bounded.
- That stretching is the physical route to **energy scaling** and dissipative soliton resonance.
- The **complex cubic-quintic Ginzburg-Landau equation** setting also mirrors **driven-open condensate coherence problems**.

What is a chirp?

Energy scaling: grow pulse duration, not peak power

A nonlinear-dynamical mechanism with photonic observables and nonequilibrium-coherence analogies.

Question and roadmap

What controls existence and energy scaling when the dispersion sign changes?

Main answer

NGD: DSR is intrinsic → AGD: DSR is conditional

The AGD resonance line must lie inside the adiabatic existence window.

Model: cubic–quintic complex Ginzburg–Landau equation

$$\frac{\partial a}{\partial z} = -\sigma a + (\alpha - i\beta) \frac{\partial^2 a}{\partial t^2} + (\kappa + i\gamma) |a|^2 a - (\kappa\zeta + i\chi) |a|^4 a$$

Physical terms

- σ saturated loss / vacuum stability
- α spectral filtering / gain bandwidth
- β GDD: $\beta > 0$ NGD, $\beta < 0$ AGD
- κ, ζ cubic SAM and SAM saturation
- γ, χ cubic SPM and quintic SPM saturation

Strong-chirp ansatz

$$a(z, t) = \sqrt{P(t)} \exp[i\varphi(t) - iqz], \quad \Omega(t) = d\varphi/dt$$

E.PODIVILOV, V.L.KALASHNIKOV, JETP Lett. 82, 467 (2005).

- rapid phase, slow envelope
- conservative GDD/SPM dominate dissipative terms
- large chirp; moderate-chirp states require full CGLE numerics

Approximation scope

Analytical admissibility \neq complete cavity model; noise, gain relaxation and finite spectral resolution enter later.

Dimensionless map: turn algebra into geometry

$$C = \alpha\gamma/(\beta\kappa), \quad \Sigma = \zeta\sigma/\kappa, \quad \tilde{\chi} = \chi/(\gamma\zeta), \quad \tilde{\Delta}^2 = \beta\zeta\Delta^2/\gamma, \quad \tilde{E} = E \times \kappa\sqrt{\zeta/\gamma\beta}$$

Interpretation

- C : relative strength of filtering to dispersion and SAM to SPM
- Σ : scaled saturated loss; positive value stabilizes the vacuum
- $\tilde{\chi}$: saturable or self-enhancing quintic phase nonlinearity
- $D_a = -\tilde{\Delta}^2 < 0$ is used for AGD to avoid "negative bandwidth $\tilde{\Delta}^2$ " language

Message: existence domains are readable as 2D slices and master diagram.

Physical admissibility

NGD $\beta > 0, C > 0$
 $D_a > 0$

AGD $\beta < 0, C < 0$
 $D_a < 0$

Master diagram in NGD

NGD baseline: physical branch and truncated spectra

NGD physical branches in the (C, Σ) plane

Truncated Rayleigh-Jeans/Lorentz-like spectral profiles

- Finite spectral support: $|\tilde{\Omega}| \leq \tilde{\Delta}$.
- $\tilde{\chi}$ mainly deforms bandwidth and curvature.
- NGD provides the clean reference branch for DSR.

NGD: DSR survives finite quintic SPM

Definition used here

$$\lim_{\{\Sigma \rightarrow 0^+\}} E_{\{NGD\}}(C^*, \Sigma, \tilde{\chi}) = \infty$$

while peak power stays bounded

- DSR is the scalable edge of the NGD chirped branch.
- Finite quintic SPM shifts the resonance location.
- Positive $\tilde{\chi}$ moves it to larger C ; negative $\tilde{\chi}$ to smaller C .

Conclusion: finite $\tilde{\chi}$ deforms NGD DSR; it does not remove it.

AGD: strongly chirped branch exists only in a finite window

AGD fixed- $\tilde{\chi}$ slice ($\tilde{\chi} = 1.5$): positive scale $D_a = -\tilde{\Delta}^2 > 0$

Key restrictions

$$\beta < 0, C < 0, \tilde{\chi} > 0, D_a > 0$$

$$0 < \Sigma < \min\{\Sigma_{th}(C, \tilde{\chi}), \Sigma_Q(C, \tilde{\chi})\}$$

- AGD has a real strongly chirped branch only on the minus branch.
- Outside this window, weakly chirped AGD solitons may still exist.
- Only the strongly chirped AGD branch is relevant to AGD DSR scaling.

$\Sigma_{th}(C, \tilde{\chi})$ is defined by a condition of $D_a > 0$:

$$\tilde{\chi} > \frac{3}{C+4}$$

$\Sigma_Q(C, \tilde{\chi})$ is defined by a requirement that the solution must be real:

$$\Sigma_Q = \frac{(C-2)^2}{16(1-C\tilde{\chi})}$$

AGD spectra: two-horn core and algebraic wings

Structured core with central depression; wings decay algebraically

Near resonance: normalized core nearly invariant; energy mostly changes a scalar prefactor

AGD differs qualitatively from NGD: no hard truncation, but finite energy due to $\propto |\tilde{\Omega}|^{-3}$ tails.

AGD DSR is conditional: resonance line must be reachable

$$\text{AGD resonance locus: } 1 + C\tilde{\chi} = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad C_{DSR}(\tilde{\chi}) = -1/\tilde{\chi}$$

AGD master diagram: vertical asymptotes at $C = -1/\tilde{\chi}$

But actual DSR requires

$$C_{DSR} \in \text{AGD existence window}$$

$$\Sigma \rightarrow 0^+: \quad \tilde{\chi} > 1$$

- AGD resonance is not automatic.
- Quintic saturable SPM must be strong enough.
- The criterion is geometric: the DSR line $C = -1/\tilde{\chi} \cap$ DS existence window $\neq \emptyset$.

Two correlation times: spectral self-similarity in time domain

short scale: $\ell \sim \pi/\tilde{\Omega}_{\text{cut}}$
 long scale: $\rho \sim \tilde{\Omega}_{\text{core}}^{-1}$

Interpretation: short “granularity” scale versus long collective coherence scale.

Stability: analytical AGD existence is not enough

Representative stable point table-top envelope and two-horn spectral core persist.

- Noise test: linearized perturbation around reconstructed AGD DS.
- Survival criterion: single pulse, perturbation below cutoff, high spectral correlation.
- Stable islands are displaced from exact resonance.

Thermodynamic interpretation: NGD turbulence \leftrightarrow AGD BEC

NGD

semi-incoherent DS as turbulence analogue

- **Spectrum:** truncated Lorentz / Rayleigh–Jeans form
- **Two scales:** $\ell = \pi/\Omega_{cut}$ and $\rho = 1/\Omega_{core}$ decouple near DSR
- **Thermo:** entropy H_s grows; effective temperature can turn negative
- **Limit:** single DS becomes metastable \rightarrow multi-DS “thermalization”

$$S_n^{gd}(\Omega) \propto (\Omega_{core}^2 + \Omega^2)^{-1} \Theta(\Omega_{cut}^2 - \Omega^2)$$

Key conclusion: DSR is a turbulence-like spectral condensation with entropy growth.

AGD

weakly dissipative BEC analogy

- **Spectrum:** two-horn core; algebraic $|\Omega|^{-3}$ wings; no intrinsic but external hard cutoff
- **DSR condition:** $1 + C\tilde{\chi} = 0$ must lie inside the AGD existence window
- **Coherence:** short bandwidth scale and long core-controlled scale coexist
- **BEC link:** mass/energy scaling in open, bandwidth-limited condensate analogues

$$C_{DSR} = -1/\tilde{\chi}, \quad \tilde{\chi} > 1 \ (\Sigma \rightarrow 0^+)$$

Key conclusion: AGD gives a structural BEC analogy through kinetic-sign and two-scale coherence

Unified thermodynamic picture: strong chirp turns a DS into a nonequilibrium many-mode object

Two-scale coherence creates DS microstates

Two-scale coherent structure induced by a bounded spectrum

VLADIMIR L. KALASHNIKOV *et al.* Phys. Rev. A 111, 043529 (2025).

The entropy H_s rises with energy in the DSR region.

Main message: the spectral cut-off sets the short scale ℓ , while the spectral core sets the long scale ρ . When $\rho \gg \ell$, one DS contains many internal coherent cells, $N_{micro} \sim \rho/\ell$. The growth of this microstate number with energy gives the DS a thermodynamic meaning and links it to entropy growth and eventual multi-soliton “thermalization.”

DSR as thermodynamic coherent matter

Thank Norges Forskningsråd (#303347 (UNLOCK), #326503 (MIR))

Adiabatic theory does not merely describe a soliton; it reveals a universal mechanism of far-from-equilibrium coherent self-organization.

Fundamental conclusion

- Strong chirp creates two coherence scales in a bounded spectrum.
- Scale separation creates microstates inside one localized DS.
- Entropy, temperature and multi-soliton transitions become meaningful.

DSR

two scales

microstates

Outlook

- DSR becomes a thermodynamic route to scalable coherent matter.
- Energy scaling in photonics maps to mass scaling in BEC-like systems.
- Controlled loss, bandwidth and nonlinearity may enable macroscopic coherent / quantum states.

Turbulence Rayleigh–Jeans-like spectra; entropy growth; mode thermalization

DS theory <-->

BEC mass scaling; open condensates; route to macroscopic coherent states

DSR links nonlinear coherent structures with nonequilibrium thermodynamics — a design principle for scalable coherent matter.